

Scatterplot for: EXP00023 2021-02-15 (Experiment)

Report date: February 15, 2021 14:35

X-axis = 5 mg treated 2 21

Y-axis = control 02 2021

Corr coeff = 0.647713

Slope = 0.707540, Intercept = 1.909992

Spot count = 121

